

Bharatamine—A Novel Protoberberine Alkaloid of Aberrant Biogenetic Origin from *Alangium lamarckii* Thw.

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The structure elucidation and the synthesis of bharatamine, a biogenetic marvel being a protoberberine alkaloid unoxxygenated in ring D, and its regioisomer isobharatamine have been discussed in detail.

Our continuing effort directed towards the investigation of the chemical constituents of the biogenetically versatile plant *Alangium lamarckii* Thw. (N.O. Alangiaceae), we encountered a wide variety of alkaloids including some new benzoquinolizine bases^{1,2} and several novel pyridobenzoquinolizines³. From seeds of the same source, we recently reported⁴ the isolation of a unique tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloid designated as bharatamine, the structure of which has been unequivocally established as 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5,6,13,13a-tetrahydro-8H-dibenzo[a,g]quinolizine (1). Herein we describe the structure elucidation and the total syntheses of bharatamine and its regioisomer (isobharatamine) in detail.

To our knowledge, bharatamine is the first naturally occurring tetrahydroprotoberberine unoxxygenated in ring D. Since the accepted biogenetic pathway for this class of compounds requires^{5,6} an oxygen function in ring D, the genesis of this unique member of the group obviously involves a precursor other than DOPA or its equivalent for the formation of ring D. Its origin could be envisaged^{3,4} from secologanin, a common precursor of the cooccurring benzoquinolizines and pyridobenzoquinolizine alkaloids.

The procedure used for the isolation of bharatamine (1) along with the pyridobenzoquinolizine bases from the weakly basic fraction of the total alkaloids of *A. lamarckii* has already been reported⁴. This minor base obtained in ca 0.00035% yield was optically inactive. The ir band at 3160 cm⁻¹ and uv absorption at 290 nm with bathochromic shift to 310 nm in alkali indicated the presence of a phenolic tetrahydroprotoberberine skeleton in the compound. This was more clearly borne out by the mass spectral fragmentation peaks of bharatamine particularly at *m/z* 176 and 104 which must have resulted from the retro Diels-Alder cleavage of a substituted tetrahydroprotoberberine moiety.

The ¹H nmr spectrum displayed the presence of an aromatic methoxy (singlet at δ 3.84), a tetra-substituted phenyl (two one-proton singlets at δ 6.60 and 6.84) and a disubstituted phenyl (four-proton multiplet at δ 7.14) moieties. The single frequency off-resonance decoupled ¹³C nmr spectrum of bharatamine exhibited six singlets in the aromatic

region, two of them in the downfield region for the carbons attached to oxygen functions. Of the seven doublets observed, six were for aromatic carbons and the remaining upfield signal for a methine carbon. Signals were also observed for four methylene carbons as triplets in the aliphatic region in addition to a quartet for the methoxy carbon. The shift assignments of the carbons in rings C and D were done by comparing with those reported⁷ for 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline while those of rings A and B by analogy with the reported values for tetrahydroprotoberberines and benzyloquinolines⁸.

All the foregoing data thus led us to the two alternative structures, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5,6,13,13a-tetrahydro-8H-dibenzo[a,g]quinolizine (1) or its 2-methoxy-3-hydroxy isomer for bharatamine.

The gross structure of bharatamine was corroborated by its conversion to the synthetically known 2,3-dimethoxyberberine⁹ (2) by treatment with diazomethane. The relative positions of the hydroxy and methoxy groups could not be ascertained from the spectral data of bharatamine itself. Fair indication of the location of the hydroxyl group at C-2 was, however, secured by comparing the uv spectrum of the iodine oxidation product of the compound with those of the closely related protoberberines¹⁰, viz. columbamine (3) and jatrorrhizine (4). Only a partial shift of the 345 nm band to 390 nm in 0.1 N NaOH and the absence of any bathochromic shift of the same maximum in presence of sodium acetate

in the uv spectrum of this oxidation product were compatible more with the substitution pattern of 3 rather than that of 4

Bharatamine was, therefore, assigned structure 1. Finally, the structure was established by its unambiguous synthesis (Scheme 1) along with its positional isomer, isobaratamine, yet to be encountered in nature.

Scheme 1

The protoberberine skeleton of bharatamine was constructed by photochemical cyclisation^{11,12} of the enamide 6a prepared by benzylation of 5a. The resulting mixture of unsaturated and saturated lactams 7a and 8a (yield 32%) could be resolved by preparative tlc. Nevertheless, for all practical purposes, the mixture itself was reduced first by LiAlH₄ and subsequently by NaBH₄. The yield of the resulting O-benzylbharatamine 9a which was rather poor could be improved by treatment of the mixture of lactams 7a and 8a with POCl₃ followed by NaBH₄ reduction of the intermediate quaternary imminium chlorides *in situ*¹³. Finally, debenylation of 9a with hydrochloric acid afforded bharatamine (1) in 30% yield, identical in all respects with the natural product.

Isobaratamine (10), the regioisomer of bharatamine, was likewise synthesised from the dihydroiso-

quinoline 5b. The lactams 7b and 8b could not be separated. However, their presence in the mixture could be ascertained from the ¹H nmr spectrum. The reduction of the lactams by sequential treatment with POCl₃ and NaBH₄ yielded O-benzylisobaratamine, from which isobaratamine (10) could be generated by debenylation. The product could be distinguished from bharatamine on the basis of distinct ¹H nmr chemical shifts of the singlets due to the aromatic protons H-1 and H-4. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of isobaratamine was found to be similar to that of bharatamine with the expected differences in the chemical shifts of the ring A carbons.

Recently, Patil and Mali¹⁴ reported the total synthesis of both these compounds by an altogether different route.

Although bharatamine has a tetrahydroprotoberberine structure, it is most unlikely that it is biosynthesised by the same route as others of its class. The hitherto accepted^{5,6} biogenetic pathway to protoberberines from benzyloquinolines involving cyclisation of the immonium intermediates of type 11 requires activation of ring D by a suitable oxygen substituent for nucleophilic attack on the N-methylene group (Scheme 2). This explains why all the protoberberines (*e.g.* 12, 13) so far isolated have, without exception, an oxygen substituent at C-9 or C-11 and as such clearly points to an aberrant origin of bharatamine (1).

Scheme 2

The genesis of bharatamine could be visualised by invoking the involvement of the monoterpenoid secologanin^{8,4} via the glycoside 14, the common precursor of alkaloids of both 14 (benzoquinolizines) and 1β(pyridobenzoquinolizines) series encountered in the plant. The glycoside 14 could lead to a dialdehyde 15 through hydrolytic cleavage of both the glycosidic bond and dihydropyran ring as well as loss of carbomethoxy function by hydrolysis and decarboxylation. Cyclisation of this intermediate 15 to 16 followed by nucleophilic attack of the vinyl

group on the remaining aldehyde could lead to the tetracyclic intermediate **17**. Dehydration and aromatisation thereafter could lead to bharatamine (Scheme 3).

It is relevant to point out that whereas the stereochemical integrity at C-1 is retained during the biosynthesis of benzoquinolizidines and pyrido-benzoquinolizidines from **14**, bharatamine itself is optically inactive. Whether it is due to racemisation or because of its origin from both the stereoisomers of **14** is not clear.

Incidentally, decarbomethoxydihydrogambirtannine (**18**), the indole analogue of bharatamine, has also been reported¹⁷ from an *Ochrosia* species.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid-bath and are uncorrected. Optical rotation was measured on a Perkin-Elmer 141 polarimeter and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer in nujol unless otherwise stated. ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Jeol FX-100 instrument employing TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Hitachi RMU-6L instrument using the direct inlet system. Uv spectra were taken in ethanol unless mentioned otherwise on either Carl Zeiss Specord UV-VIS or PYE UNICAM SP8-300 UV-VIS spectrophoto-

mers. Light petrol refers to the fraction, b.p. 60-80°.

Isolation of bharatamine (1): An outline of the isolation procedure of bharatamine (**1**) has already been described⁹. Briefly, the total alkaloid from the methanol extract of *A. lamarckii* seeds (10 kg) was dissolved in chloroform and fractionated by successive extractions with buffers of pH 6.4, pH 4.6 and 2 N HCl. Bharatamine was obtained from the 2 N HCl extract along with the pyridobenzoquinolizine bases. Separation by column chromatography followed by crystallisation from CHCl₃ - light petrol yielded bharatamine (**1**) as light yellow needles (35 mg), m.p. 182-83° (Found: C, 76.68; H, 6.85; N, 4.73. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₉NO₉: C, 76.87; H, 6.76; N, 4.98%); [α]_D²⁵ CHCl₃ ± 0°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 206 (4.89), 290 (3.77), (0.1 N NaOH) 208 (4.84), 295 (3.91) and 310 (3.71) nm; ν_{max} 3160 and 1582 cm⁻¹; *m/z* (rel. intensity) 281 (M⁺, 89), 280 (100), 266 (15), 176 (46), 105 (37) and 104 (60); δ 2.48-4.12 (9H, m), 3.84 (3H, s), 6.60 (1H, s), 6.84 (1H, s), and 7.14 (4H, m); ¹³C nmr δ 145.2 (C-3), 144.0 (C-2), 134.4, 134.3 (C-8a, C-12a), 130.4 (C-13b), 128.7 (C-9), 126.1, 126.0, 125.7 (C-10, C-11, C-12), 125.8 (C-4a), 111.4 (C-4), 110.6 (C-1), 59.5 (C-13a), 58.5 (C-8), 55.8 (OCH₃), 51.5 (C-6), 36.5 (C-13) and 29.0 (C-5).

O-Methylbharatamine (2) hydrochloride: A solution of bharatamine (6 mg) in methanol (6 ml) was treated with a solution of freshly prepared diazomethane (generated from 2 g of nitrosomethylurea) in ether (5 ml) at 0-5° for 5 h. The product on chromatography over deactivated silica gel with light petrol-CHCl₃ (1:1) afforded O-methylbharatamine as a viscous oil. It was dissolved in 20% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml) and the solution allowed to stand at 4° for 4 h to yield O-methylbharatamine (**2**) hydrochloride as needles (5 mg), m.p. 250°. It was identified as the hydrochloride of 2,3-dimethoxyberbine by direct comparison (m.m.p., tlc, ir) with an authentic sample⁹.

2-Benzoyl-7-benzyloxy-6-methoxy-1-methylene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (6a): To a stirred solution of 7-benzyloxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline²⁵ (**5a**; 6 g, 0.02 mol) in dry benzene (250 ml) containing triethylamine (10 ml) was added dropwise a solution of benzoyl chloride (3 ml) in benzene (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 3.5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice-water and the precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride removed by filtration. Removal of solvent from the filtrate afforded a solid residue, which was crystallised from CHCl₃ - light petrol to give the enamide (**6a**) as pale yellow granules (6.0 g, 73%), m.p. 169-70°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 217 (4.56), 265 (4.25) and 306 (3.81) nm; ν_{max} 1655, 1605, 1555 and 1490 cm⁻¹; CIMS (NH₃) *m/z* 386 (M+1); δ 2.96 (2H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 3.88 (3H, s), 4.10 (2H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 4.38 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 5.12 (2H, s), 6.68 (1H, s), 7.04 (1H, s) and 7.28-7.56 (10H, m).

2-Benzoyl-6-benzyloxy-7-methoxy-1-methylene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (6b): The enamide **6b** was prepared by the same method as **6a** using

6-benzyloxy-7-methoxy-1-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline^{1a} (**5b**; 10 g, 0.035 mol), benzoyl chloride (5 ml), triethylamine (20 ml) and benzene (450 ml). The product was crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol to give **6b** as yellow granules (11.6 g, 84%), m.p. 124-26°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 240 (sh, 3.89), 265 (4.14) and 303 (3.88) nm; ν_{max} 1660, 1615, 1590 and 1490 cm^{-1} ; CIMS (NH_3) m/z 386 ($M+1$); δ 2.92 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 3.88 (3H, s), 4.08 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 4.44 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 5.16 (2H, s), 5.28 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 6.68 (1H, s), 7.04 (1H, s) and 7.28-7.60 (10H, m).

2-Benzyloxy-3-methoxy-5,6-dihydro-8H-dibenzo-[a,g]quinolizin-8-one (7a) and 2-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-5,6,13,13a-tetrahydro-8H-dibenzo[a,g]quinolizin-8-one (8a): A solution of enamide **6a** (2 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (340 ml) was irradiated for 2 h under nitrogen with a 400 W medium pressure mercury lamp using a Pyrex filter. Two more batches of **6a** (2.0 g and 1.6 g) were irradiated in the same manner. The pooled products were chromatographed over deactivated silica-gel. Elution with light petrol- CHCl_3 (3:1) afforded a yellow solid (2.10 g, 27%), which showed two spots in tlc. A part (100 mg) of the solid was subjected to preparative tlc on silica-gel in ethyl acetate-benzene (1:9). From the faster moving band, the lactam (**8a**) was obtained as a light yellow solid crystallising from CHCl_3 -light petrol in yellow granules (30 mg), m.p. 156-58°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 235 (3.88), 250 (sh, 3.77), 264 (sh, 3.72) and 278 (3.72) nm; ν_{max} 1640, 1625, 1595 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. intensity) 385 (24, M^+), 295(19), 294(86), 264(9), 234(10), 165(15), 118(60), 105(12) and 91(100); δ 2.64-3.18 (5H, m), 3.86 (3H, s), 4.78 (1H, dd, J 12 and 5 Hz), 4.92-5.08 (1H, m), 5.14 (2H, s), 6.70 (2H, s), 7.08-7.54 (8H, m) and 8.12 (1H, dd, J 7 and 2 Hz).

From the slower moving band the lactam **7a** was obtained as a yellow solid (60 mg) and crystallising from CHCl_3 -light petrol as yellow granules, m.p. 184-86°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 245 (4.13), 332 (4.35), 347 (sh, 4.28) and 365 (sh, 4.09) nm; ν_{max} 1630, 1590, 1575 and 1495 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. intensity) 383 (100, M^+), 292(21), 264(66), 249(16), 248(16), 220(19) and 91(52); δ 2.92 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 3.92 (3H, s), 4.35 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 5.20 (2H, s), 6.68 (1H, s), 6.74 (1H, s), 7.28-7.72 (9H, m) and 8.40 (1H, d, J 8 Hz).

3-Benzyloxy-2-methoxy-5,6-dihydro-8H-dibenzo-[a,g]quinolizin-8-one (7b) and 3-benzyloxy-2-methoxy-5,6,13,13a-tetrahydro-13,13a-tetrahydro-8H-dibenzo-[a,g]quinolizin-8-one (8b): The enamide **6b** (11.5 g, 0.03 mol) was irradiated in the same manner as **6a** in six batches affording a mixture (3.0 g, 26%) of lactams **7b** and **8b** which could not be resolved by preparative tlc. The ^1H nmr spectrum of the mixture showed two sets of peaks corresponding to both the lactams in the ratio 2:1, **7b**, δ 2.88 (t, J 6 Hz), 3.98 (s), 4.32 (t, J 6 Hz), 5.20 (s) and 8.42 (d, J 8 Hz), and **8b**, δ 3.90 (s), 4.74-5.04 (m), 5.14 (s) and 8.14 (dd, J 7 and 2 Hz). The mass spectrum of

the mixture showed peaks, **7b**, m/z 383 (M^+), 292, 264 and 91, **8b**, m/z 385 (M^+), 294, 266, 118 and 91.

O-Benzylbharatamine (9a): To the mixture (0.8 g) of **7a** and **8a** was added POCl_3 (4 ml) and the mixture heated at 60-80° for 2.5 h. Excess POCl_3 was distilled off under reduced pressure, the residue dried under vacuum, and then dissolved in dry methanol (50 ml). The solution was cooled to 0° and NaBH_4 (2.0 g) was added in portions with stirring which was continued for another 0.5 h after the addition was over and then kept overnight at room temperature. It was diluted with water (150 ml) and extracted with CHCl_3 . After removal of solvent, an oily residue was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with light petrol- CHCl_3 (1:1), CHCl_3 and CHCl_3 - CH_3OH (98:2) gave **9a** (0.27 g, 35%) as a gum. A part (50 mg) of this residue was further purified by preparative tlc on silica gel (ethyl acetate-diethylamine, 95:5) and precipitated from light petrol to yield **9a** as an amorphous solid (25 mg), m.p. 100-02°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 240 (3.63), 275 (3.48), 285 (sh, 3.47) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1600 and 1510 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. intensity) 371 (M^+ , 47), 370 (51), 280 (19), 266 (5), 105 (25), 104 (13) and 91 (100); δ 2.50-4.22 (9H, m), 3.86 (3H, s), 5.14 (2H, s), 6.64 (1H, s), 6.76 (1H, s) and 7.00-7.60 (9H, m).

O-Benzylisobharatamine (9b): The mixture of **7b** and **8b** (1.0 g) was treated with POCl_3 (5 ml) and the product was identically reduced with NaBH_4 (2.5 g) as above. Chromatography of the product over silica gel and elution with 10-25% CHCl_3 in light petrol afforded a solid which on crystallisation from CHCl_3 -light petrol gave **9b** as pale yellow granules (0.3 g, 31%) m.p. 130-31°; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 238 (4.37), 263 (sh, 4.34), 270 (sh, 4.48) and 280 (4.60) nm; ν_{max} 1610 and 1510 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. intensity) 371 (M^+ , 37), 370 (25), 280 (78), 105 (100), 104(41) and 91 (92); δ 2.36-4.18 (9H, m), 3.92 (3H, s), 5.14 (2H, s), 6.68 (1H, s), 6.80 (1H, s) and 7.04-7.64 (9H, m).

Bharatamine (1): A solution of **9a** (0.22 g, 0.0006 mol) in ethanol (7 ml) containing concentrated HCl (7 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. It was then cooled to 0° and neutralised with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. Extraction with CHCl_3 and removal of solvent afforded **1** as a viscous residue (0.15 g). Purification by preparative tlc on silica gel (ethyl acetate-diethylamine, 95:5) and recrystallisation from CHCl_3 -light petrol gave **1** as pale yellow granules (0.05 g, 30%), m.p. 179-80°. The synthetic material was identical in all respect with the natural product (m.m.p., uv, ir, ms and ^1H nmr).

Isobharatamine (10): Debonylation of **9b** (0.19 g, 0.0005 mol) by the same procedure as above yielded isobharatamine (**10**) crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol as light yellow needles (0.045 g, 23%), m.p. 124-25° (Found: C, 76.75; H, 6.71; N, 4.85. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2$: C, 76.87; H, 6.76; N, 4.98%); λ_{max} (log ϵ) 285 (3.51) nm; ν_{max} 3520 and

1 610 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. intensity) 281 (86, M^+), 280 (100), 177 (14), 176 (51), 105 (37), 104 (55) and 103 (16); δ 2.44-4.20 (9H, m), 3.88 (3H, s), 5.56 (1H, br s), 6.68 (1H, s), 6.73 (1H, s) and 7.00-7.20 (4H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ 145.3 (C-2), 144.1 (C-3), 134.3 (C-8a, C-12a), 129.0 (C-13b), 128.6 (C-9), 127.3 (C-4a), 126.2, 126.0, 125.8 (C-10, C-11, C-12), 114.4 (C-4), 107.9 (C-1), 59.6 (C-13a), 58.5 (C-8), 56.0 (OCH_3), 51.3 (C-6), 36.6 (C-13) and 28.6 (C-5).

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